

denum, tellurium, antimony and arsenic electrodes, respectively. These potential increments correspond to $1/4$, $2/15$, $1/15$ and $1/15$ of the electrode surface being covered with oxygen doublets as compared with $2/3$ in the case of chromium. If the surface area of the electrode covered with oxygen doublets is taken as a measure of passivity, then those metals should be placed with respect to their passivity in the following order: Cr, Mo, Sb, As (Tourky, Issa and Khalifa, unpublished).

Further, when the electrodes are subjected to the action of hydrogen and to high vacuum, a good portion of the passivating film including metal oxide and oxygen doublets is removed whereby the potentials become more negative than those observed in aerated solutions.

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STUDIES IN THE PASSIVITY OF CHROMIUM. PART II. THE EFFECT OF ANIONS ON THE PASSIVATING FILM ON CHROMIUM

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From the study of the effect of anions on the passivity of chromium it is shown that the passivating action goes in the order: Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- . It is also shown that the potentials set in presence of oxygen are more positive than those set in presence of nitrogen. Similarly the potentials obtained in absence of chloride ions are more positive than in their presence.

In the previous investigation (this issue, p. 465) it has been shown that the passivity of chromium is due to the presence on the metal surface of an oxide film overlaid by an oxygen film which covers only $2/3$ of the area of the oxide surface. Müller (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1931, 37, 328; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, A68, 159) studied the effect of different acids on the activation of passive chromium and found it to depend upon the permeabilities of the different anions through the pores of the passivating film. The acid anions offered a frictional resistance both to the emergence of the metal ions from the lattice and to the entrance of hydrogen ions into the double layer. This was concluded from the fact that the liberation of hydrogen from acids by active chromium was greater, the smaller the radius of the acid anion. Further evidence as to the effect of anions can be gained from a study of the electrodic behaviour of massive chromium (which is easily passivated) during the initial build up of the electrode potential when present in solution containing them, under a variety of conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electrode used in this investigation is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of a cylinder fitted by a rubber tubing to the shorter limb of a U-shaped glass tubing so that only the upper surface is exposed to the solution. Electrical contact here was also made (as in Part I) through a copper wire, soldered to the inner side of the electrode.

Stick Cr.

The anions studied were the chloride, the phthalate, the sulphate, the nitrate and the borate. The solutions were prepared from the Analar products by dissolving them in twice distilled water. The concentrations used varied between 0.01 M and 0.1 M.

The electrode potential measurements were made in (a) unstirred aerated solutions, (b) unstirred solutions freed from oxygen by bubbling nitrogen through, (c) stirred solutions by bubbling nitrogen and (d) stirred solutions by bubbling oxygen.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

The curves shown in Fig. 2 represent the variation of potential with time in the solutions mentioned during 30 minutes following immersion in presence of air. The curves shown in Fig. 3 represent the same behaviour while bubbling nitrogen. Fig. 4 represents the effect of the prevailing atmosphere on the electrode behaviour.

DISCUSSION

With massive chromium the time-potential curves obtained in all solutions of the aforementioned anions, possess the same shape and are characterised by an initial rapid change to more positive potentials, followed by a less steeper one. This behaviour is attributed to the tendency of the electrode to become more passive. The passivating

action of the anions goes in the following order: Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , and NO_3^- . In this arrangement we restricted ourselves to the neutral solutions applied in order to exclude as far as possible the effect of p_{H} on the electrode potential. The phthalate solution being acidic in character leads to a more positive potential, whereas the borate solution being alkaline sets up a more negative one. This order repeats itself under all conditions studied, indicating that the variation in the magnitude of potential set in all cases is to a great extent affected by the anions present in the solution.

The somewhat active potential observed in chloride solutions is due to the high penetrating power of the chloride ions which lowers the electrical resistance of the corrosion product, assisting thus in the depolarisation of oxygen deposited on the electrode surface. The sulphate ions are more voluminous and less penetrating and thus less activating. Another factor is the coagulating effect of the anions on the precipitated oxide. Owing to the weaker coagulating power of the chloride, a longer time is required for the accumulation of the corrosion products. With the polyvalent ions the corrosion product is precipitated more rapidly. Although the nitrate ion is univalent and possesses thus a weaker coagulating effect, yet by virtue of its oxidising power, the metal surface is probably more readily covered with the passivating film.

The effects of anions manifest themselves clearly on varying their concentrations between 0.01 M and 0.1 M. Experiments have shown that while increase of the concentration of the nitrate has no effect on the potential, that of the sulphate leads to more positive values in contradistinction from the chloride ions which produce an opposite effect.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

Curve a refers to initial potentials set by stick Cr
Curve b refers to potentials 3 hrs. after immersion.

The effect of chloride ions was further confirmed by measuring the potentials set by the massive chromium electrodes in buffer solutions made 0.1 *M* with respect to chloride ions. As is apparent from the curves shown in Fig. 5, it is apparent that in such solutions the potentials are less positive than those set in chloride-free buffers (Fig. 3, Part I, *loc. cit.*) although they tend always to become more positive with time.

Fig. 4 indicates the effect of the prevailing atmosphere on the potentials set. It is apparent that in presence of oxygen the potentials are more positive than in presence of air and these in turn are more positive than in nitrogen atmosphere. The effect of the prevailing atmosphere suggests the possibility that the electrode behaves as metal-metal oxide-oxygen electrode, the potential of which is dependent upon the prevailing gaseous atmosphere (Tourky and Moussa, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 7 50; 1949, 1297).

The facts obtained in this investigation, viz., (a) the depolarising action of chloride ions, (b) the effect of the prevailing nitrogen atmosphere, and those obtained in the previous investigation, (i) the effect of heating in vacuum of hydrogen on the passivating film, (ii) the more positive potentials obtained by the different electrodes than the thermodynamic value, together with the fact that (c) the temperature coefficient of chromium and similar electrodes are large and variable (Tourky and Khairy, *ibid.*, 1952, 2626) suggests that the passivating film involves an oxide overlayers with an oxygen film.

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